

MODERN MANIPULATION AND VIOLATION OF AUTONMY IN *QUITTERS, INC.* BY STEPHEN KING

STEPHEN KING'İN *QUITTERS, INC.* ÖYKÜSÜNDE MODERN MANİPÜLASYON VE ÖZERKLİĞİN İHLALİ

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Abstract

Stephen King is considered one of the most prolific and influential writers of modern horror literature. What distinguishes him is that his stories transcend superficial narratives of fear, instead deeply reflecting the darker aspects of human psychology, societal anxieties, and the pressures of modern life. The story of *Quitters, Inc.*, from his 1978 book *Night Shift*, stands out as a striking allegory of the corporate manipulation that threatens individual freedom. The pressure Dick Morrison faces during his attempt to quit smoking is linked to Michel Foucault's concept of "surveillance society" and B. F. Skinner's principles of "operant conditioning". Morrison's psychological transformation, the ethical dilemmas he faces, and the challenges he experienced in the name of individual freedom are analyzed within the context of Kant's deontological ethics and the limits of utilitarianism. Furthermore, the elements of fear, anxiety, and dark humor in the story reflect the fundamental themes of dystopian literature and draw parallels with today's systems of algorithmic control and media manipulation. King's simple language, psychological analyses, and escalating tension powerfully reflect the effects of manipulation on the individual. Ultimately, *Quitters, Inc.* is a warning about the dangers of surrendering one's free will in the hope of recovery.

Keywords: Horror Literature, Surveillance Society, Institutional Power, Manipulation, *Quitters, Inc.*, Stephen King.

Özet

Stephen King, modern korku edebiyatının en üretken ve etkili yazarlarından biri olarak kabul edilir. Onu farklı kılan, hikâyelerini yalnızca yüzeysel korku anlatıları olarak değil insan psikolojisinin karanlık yönlerini, toplumsal kaygıları ve modern yaşamın baskılarını derinlemesine yansıtmasıdır. 1978’de yayımlanan *Night Shift* öykü koleksiyonundaki *Quitters, Inc.* öyküsü, bireyin özgürlüğünü tehdit eden kurumsal manipülasyonun çarpıcı bir alegorisi olarak göze çarpar. Öyküde sigarayla bırakma sürecinde Dick Morrison’ın maruz kaldığı baskı, Michel Foucault’nun “gözetim toplumu” kavramı ve B. F. Skinner’in “edimsel koşullanma” ilkeleriyle ilişkilendirilmiştir. Morrison’ın yaşadığı psikolojik dönüşüm, karşılaştığı etik ikilemler ve bireysel özgürlük adı altında yaşadığı zorluklar ise Kant’ın deontolojik etiği ve faydacılığın sınırları bağlamında değerlendirilmiştir. Ayrıca öyküdeki korku, kaygı ve kara mizah unsurları distopik edebiyatın temel temalarını yansıtırken, günümüzdeki algoritmik kontrol ve medya manipülasyonu sistemleriyle de paralellik kurar. King’in sade dili, psikolojik çözümlenmeleri ve giderek artan gerilimi, manipülasyonun birey üzerindeki etkilerini güçlü biçimde yansıtır. Sonuçta *Quitters, Inc.*, bireyin özgür iradesini teslim ederek iyileşme umuduna sığınmasının ne denli tehlikeli olabileceğine dair uyarandır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Korku Edebiyatı, Gözetim Toplumu, Kurumsal Güç, Manipülasyon, *Quitters Inc.*, Stephen King.

1. INTRODUCTION

Stephen King is one of the most productive and influential figures in modern horror literature. What gives him this title is that he takes his works beyond being merely superficial horror narratives. His narratives, style of narration, and characters serve as a deep probe into the dark and secret labyrinths of human psychology, social anxieties, and the individual's sensitivities against the various pressures imposed by modern life. Rather than limiting horror to purely supernatural or grotesque imagery, King skilfully uses the reader's unexpressed fears and the tension created in individuals by social realities, making his stories a mirror of a person open to psychological and sociological interpretations and criticisms. In this context, his short story *Quitters, Inc.* from his 1978 collection *Night Shift* stands out as a touching and disturbingly real example of fiction that addresses the potential pressure of institutional power and the resulting manipulation on the individual and the ethical dimensions of manipulation.

Quitters, Inc. highlights the desire to get rid of cigarette addiction and strikingly demonstrates how other addictions like this can be eliminated through an extraordinary and unethical corporate intervention. The story begins with the main character, Dick Morrison, applying to a mysterious and dangerous company called “Quitters, Inc.” upon the advice of his friend in order to end his cigarette addiction. The company briefly but comprehensively outlines the methods and processes of getting rid of addiction. However, this company applies a conditioning system based on fear and the threat of violence, which is very different from traditional therapy and resistance methods against addiction. In this way, it completely takes control of Morrison's life in order to control him. The power of the company's surveillance capacity at all times and from everywhere, the open expression of potential harm to family members in order to resist addiction and the cruel punishments for failure transform the story from being a narrative of fighting addiction into a dystopian allegory. This situation causes a deep ethical dilemma about how manipulable individual freedom can be and whether the end justifies the means.

This article will critically analyze how the concepts of individual freedom and free will become the target of corporate manipulation in Stephen King's story *Quitters, Inc.*, how fear and the threat of violence are used as a means of control, and how ethical boundaries are ignored in this process. The article will examine the effects of the psychological and sociological dimensions of the control mechanisms implemented by the company on the individual, taking into account Michel Foucault's theories of surveillance and power and B. F. Skinner's principles of behavioural conditioning.

In this context, the ethical problems in the context of the purpose-means relationship presented by the story will be evaluated within the framework of Noel Carroll's theories of fear. Thus, the effect of the narrative on the reader, the relationship of dystopia with the experienced reality, and the potential for social criticism will be revealed. This multidimensional and wide-ranging analysis will reveal that the story is not just a horror narrative, but also a hidden and critical allegory about the pressure on the individual by institutional power dynamics in modern society and the invisible erosion of freedom.

2. THEROTICAL EXPLANATION OF MANIPULATION AND ITS APPLICATION IN *QUITTERS INC.*

Manipulation in Stephen King's *Quitters, Inc.* is not a simple persuasion mechanism. It targets and blurs individual autonomy through psychological coercion and systematic fear instillation, which seems simple but is much more profound and dangerous. In this section, we will examine in depth the control mechanisms and techniques implemented by the company "Quitters, Inc." in the story in the light of various manipulation theories. Thus, we will analyze the destructive effect of these unethical methods on the psychology and behaviour of the main character, Dick Morrison, with a more academic eye. The company's purpose, vision and activities present a striking allegory that will draw attention not only to the potential dangers of individual-institutional relationships in modern society, but also to the bond between the governing party, who holds the balance of power, and the governed party.

"Manipulation is a means by which a person is gotten to do something that the person was not initially inclined to do." (Noggle, 2021). This can be considered as the shortest definition of manipulation. Dijk made this definition as follows; "Manipulating people involves manipulating their minds, that is, people's beliefs, such as the knowledge, opinions and ideologies which in turn control their actions." (Van Dijk, 2006). In fact, if we were to make a detailed analysis, although manipulation is discussed in a wide spectrum in ethical and psychological literature, it is basically defined as the effort of a person or group to direct the thoughts, feelings, beliefs or behaviours of another person or group in line with their own interests through unspecified, covert or deceptive means (Noggle, 2021). Manipulation is the attempt to influence another person's behaviour usually through deception or exploitation of person's weaknesses. Manipulation differs from persuasion and coercion. Coercion always involves irresistible incentives, while manipulation involves more subtle and covert influence. The success of manipulation attempt is closely related to the person's feeling that he or she is the object of a manipulative situation (Rudinow, 1978). These definitions not only clearly distinguish manipulation from persuasion, but also indicate that the persuasion process is generally transparent, argumentative, and based on the conscious consent of the individual. However, what distinguishes manipulation from persuasion is that the victim is not fully informed and does not consent, or their free will is undermined by threats or deception.

While Robert Cialdini's famous principles of persuasion reciprocity, commitment and consistency, social proof, authority, likability, and scarcity generally describe consensual and ethically acceptable persuasion processes, (Cialdini, 1984) the persuasion process at "Quitters Inc." represents an extreme, distorted, and grotesque application of these principles, a clear indication that it is not a persuasion process. Instead of persuasion, the company directly violates the individual's freedom by using elements of force, coercion, threats, and behavioural conditioning. In this context, manipulation is defined as "causing others to act in ways that serve the manipulator's purposes" and in this process, the criticism that "the victim's freedom is not actually undermined by manipulation, but is treated as if agency were devoid of its distinctively human characteristics is prominent. This philosophical and ethical distinction closely coincides with Dick Morrison's experience with Quitters, Inc., where Morrison's act of quitting smoking is shaped by his own initial desire, but the way he continues to do so is seen as the product of a purely external and coercive manipulation implemented by the company (Yaffe, 2003).

The company's well-intentioned attitude fighting addictions changes after a while with the tyrannical side of the dark managerial power in a dystopian world. It reflects this tyrannical side in the treatment process that it introduces as good. It exposes the most unethical principles of behavioral psychology with the techniques it applies to help people quit addiction under treatment. In fact, in this story, our author Stephen King interprets B. F. Skinner's operant conditioning principles differently. This interpretation creates a dystopian and fear-intensive story. While Skinner puts forward the thesis that the way to gain behaviour can be through positive or negative reinforcement and punishments in his theories (Skinner, 1953), the company uses extreme negative reinforcements by threatening the character's family life in a way that will be in his favour and against the individual. This can be seen as one of the most frightening ways to gain behaviour. This situation can be explained as the practicalization of the experimental process that Skinner theoretically put forward and brought to real life.

The company uses various violent techniques to get Morrison to quit his addiction. The basis of the manipulation they apply is the threats of physical and psychological violence against Dick Morrison's family, making other threats that will be applied in the continuation of the person's addiction more likely. After the principles Dick signs, it is stated that if he continues to smoke, his wife Lucretia and his son Andrew will first be subjected to physical violence, then they will not do what they say, and if his addiction does not decrease, he will gradually face more serious consequences. This is reflected in the story as follows: "The first time, we will give your wife an electric shock. The second time, we will take care of her. The third time, we will take care of your child. The fourth time, we will kill you." (King, 1978). The direct and merciless nature of these threats is not only aimed at eliminating Dick's smoking behaviour, but also at completely destroying his personal security area and most basic human ties on both a psychological and physical level. The damage caused by this situation stands out as a striking example of how a person's behavior can be conditioned by external and frightening stimuli. Thus, the physical and psychological damage caused by addiction is replaced by the mental and physical damage caused by manipulation.

Zygmunt Bauman's concept of "liquid fear" summarizes Dick's experiences of fear. "Fear is the name we give to our uncertainty: to our ignorance of the threat and of what is to be done what can and what can't be to stop it in its tracks or to fight it back if stopping it is beyond our power." (Bauman, 2006). This constant and unembodied threat mechanism that settles into Dick's life affects every moment of his life, showing how powerfully seizing and pervasive fear can be as a control mechanism. Fear is not only an emotional response in the story, but also functions as a deliberately designed means of control. The constant state of fear to which Dick is subjected causes him to become a reactive and conditioned subject rather than an active agent. Thus, the company replaces Dick's desire to smoke with an inhibitory response equivalent to the fear of harming his family.

The manipulation implemented by the company "Quitters, Inc." does not only include physical threats, but is also supported by constant surveillance and a complete violation of privacy. The company's ability to monitor Dick and his family at any time and from anywhere reminds us of the book 1984. Michel Foucault's concept of the "Panopticon and theories of disciplinary power" can help us understand the concept of surveillance. Designed and proposed by Jeremy Bentham, the Panopticon shows that individuals are in an architectural structure where they are constantly watched, but they do not know when they are being watched. As a result of this situation, the individual is aware that they are being watched, which leads them to regulate their own behavior with an internalized self-discipline. Because the possibility of being watched at any moment and the fear of this encourages conformity without direct external pressure. The surveillance mechanism in "Quitters, Inc." has a similar function. Dick spends his days with the feeling that he is constantly being watched, even though he does not know where the company is.

This perception, which is formed by anxiety, not only results in a tangible return of Dick's desire to smoke, but also a constant and internal anxiety due to psychological pressure (Foucault, 1995). This constant surveillance threatens individual privacy and private space, causing it to disappear completely. Dick's entire life becomes a watchable spectacle by the company at all times. This seriously threatens his ability to act and think freely. The totalitarian dimension of the surveillance system makes Dick a victim of a "Big Brother" type of control. This situation, just like in the 1984 book, creates a permanent psychological pressure on him, not just a physical threat. When we look at the story from this perspective, sometimes the situation of being imprisoned in a building brings to mind Goffman's prison. Erving Goffman's concept of "total institutions" defines places where an individual's entire life is controlled and isolated from the outside world. The practices of the company in *Quitters, Inc.* reveal the power to have a say in Dick's thoughts and behaviors by imprisoning him in a kind of invisible total institution. The isolation of his behaviors and thoughts from external factors and the reshaping of them in line with the company's goals directly show who has the power (Weinstein, 1982).

The fact that the company's manipulation is not limited to external threats and surveillance causes a deep conditioning and internalized fear to emerge in Dick Morrison's psychology. The desire to smoke gives way to fear over time. The deep phobia of potential punishment puts the individual in a dilemma between his desires and fears. This process is closely related to the addiction and control themes that King frequently addresses in his works, and while Dick is getting rid of an addiction, he becomes a victim of the fear and control created by the company as a result of the manipulation. This situation can overlap with Slav Zizek's criticisms of the freedom of the individual in modern society and the individual being made dependent on the system or power. In this context, Zizek argues that addiction can be interpreted not only as substance addiction, but also as addiction to systems or fear, and observes that today's methods of eliminating addictions also create another addiction (Zizek, 2006).

The company uses its power and manipulative aspects to prevent Dick from using his will and personal motivations. His decision not to smoke is no longer a health decision he makes with his own free will, but rather an obligation dictated by fear, and is intended to be stopped. This situation is one of the clearest indicators of how a person's behavior can become psychologically mechanical and conditioned when under constant threat. Stephen King has directly or indirectly mentioned this theme in many of his works. In general, his criticisms of the misuse of scientific knowledge by certain powers, the simplification of human psychology, and the inhuman potential caused by the control of corporate power provided by technology have been prominent themes in many of his works. The character of Vincent Donatti in *Quitters, Inc.* stands as a striking embodiment of this criticism. Donatti is a figure who simply reflects the complex psychological processes of the individual, does not approach it from a human perspective, sees it only as a mechanism that reacts, and applies it by disregarding the ethical limits of scientific methods. King's character description can be seen as a strong warning about the potential dangers of behavioral conditioning and its destructive effects on human will. This observation is a statement that clearly reveals how manipulation is not just an external pressure, but also how it turns the individual's internal fears and weaknesses against the individual. Dick's inner life, beyond the suppression of his desire to smoke, is shaped by a constant panic and expectation of threat, causing a new addiction to form. This manipulative effect negatively affects his psychological health and quality of life, allowing for health problems.

3. LITERARY REPRESENTATION OF INDIVIDUAL AUTONOMY AND ETHICAL DILEMMAS

Stephen King's *Quitters, Inc.* is not only an examination of how manipulation is applied and its effects, but also a powerful discussion area on individual autonomy, free will and ethical responsibilities.

By examining Dick Morrison's negative experiences while quitting smoking, it questions the extent to which an individual's free choices in modern life are shaped by external forces and how moral boundaries can be violated for seemingly "well-intentioned" purposes. In this section, we will examine the paradox of free will in the story, the ethical conflict between the ends and means of those in power, and the effect of manipulation on the victim.

Dick Morrison's decision to quit smoking initially seems like a personal choice made with his own free will, but the way he continues this decision reflects the fundamental paradox of the story as a necessity. With the threat and coercion techniques applied by the company, Morrison's continued choice becomes an absolute necessity. Immanuel Kant's deontological understanding of ethics argues that the basis of moral action is duty consciousness and the categorical imperative, while emphasizing that the moral value of actions is based on whether the action itself is universally right, rather than its consequences. "Act as though the maxim of your action were to become, through your will, a universal law of nature." (Kant, 2002). When viewed from this Kantian perspective, the methods of "Quitters, Inc." appear as immoral actions. Because the actions are imposed on Dick by the company and are dictated by an external threat and fear. This situation strikingly demonstrates how dependent and conditional even an action taken "freely" by an individual is, and the manipulative approaches of the company.

The story includes questions about whether even a "good" result such as quitting smoking is a true victory of freedom when it is achieved not as a result of conflicts and struggles in the individual's inner world but as a result of fear originating from outside. Dick is under constant pressure to continue the act of not smoking. This situation leads to a new kind of captivity that affects every moment of his life and leads to an addiction to fear. This is another criticism that emphasizes that individual freedom is not only related to the capacity to make choices, but also to the internal and autonomous motivations on which choices are based. The events that take place under the name of Dick's "liberation" actually occur when he submits to the control mechanism of a new system. This once again reveals that true liberation is not possible. It prompts us to think again about the concept of free will. The idea of an individual realizing his own thoughts in such a manipulative modern life is seen as a dream.

The philosophy of "Quitters, Inc." is based primarily on a utilitarian approach. There is a belief that any means can be used to achieve a result that appears beneficial to society and the individual, such as quitting smoking. Utilitarianism evaluates the moral rightness of actions by the quantity of the results or benefits they produce (Mill, 2004). The company aims to extend Dick's life and thus create more happiness by eliminating the health problems and costs of smoking under the guise of a well-intentioned intervention. However, behind this happiness or benefit lies physical violence, psychological torture and complete violation of individual rights.

The story harshly criticizes the ethical limits of this utilitarian approach. King intends to show how even a seemingly well-intentioned goal can become distorted and unacceptable when achieved through inhumane actions and immoral proposals. The company's "the end justifies the means" mentality has been subject to a barrage of criticism, as it fundamentally contradicts universal human rights and morality. This criticism is a warning, especially in modern societies, of the dangers of manipulative and potentially totalitarian interventions that can be implemented under the guise of "the good of society" or "the betterment of the individual". The story is a literary warning of how a therapy or recovery process for combating addiction can become a tool of oppression and how it can be used by the wrong powers when ethical principles are deviated from.

Dick Morrison's response to manipulation is, quite literally, a complex journey from a victim's psychological resistance to complete surrender. Initially showing his anger and denial about the company's methods, Dick is forced to surrender more and more to fear as he realizes the seriousness of the threats. This surrender is not only the result of the threat of physical violence, but also of psychological isolation and internalized oppression.

By forcing Dick to be part of the system, the company prevents him from receiving support from outside, thus breaking his resistance and integrating him into the system.

This constant psychological pressure that Dick is subjected to and the “Big Brother”-like surveillance from the 1984 book also reflects on the reader, creating discomfort and empathy. Dick’s inability to reflect his own will and his unwavering compliance with the rules imposed by the company symbolize the potential helplessness of the modern individual in the face of institutional authority. This brings to mind the struggles that King’s characters often face against the psychological pressures they are subjected to, but in *“Quitters, Inc.”* this struggle ends in a surrender on behalf of the individual and free will.

4. ALLEGORY OF CORPORATE POWER AND SOCIAL REFLECTIONS

In Stephen King’s *Quitters, Inc.*, Dick Morrison’s personal struggle provides a profound allegory of the effects of institutional power on the individual in modern societies, an allegory of the ways in which manipulation is exercised by whom. The corporation becomes not just an institution for quitting smoking, but an authority figure that obtains consent through manipulation and threats. In this section, we will examine the symbolic meanings of “Quitters, Inc.” as a corporation, why it is a part of dystopian literature, and the story’s parallels with forms of social manipulation under modernity today.

The company, “Quitters, Inc.”, is not only a power in the service sector, but also an allegory of the anonymous, powerful, and oppressive corporate powers in modern societies. In the story, the company’s activities are highly secretive, its managers are inaccessible, and its methods are implemented with strict bureaucratic discipline. In such stories in literature, corporate structures are often described as “characters” in their own right. The absolute control of these structures over individual lives and their potential moral deviations are symbolized as representations of the company and the structures. In such narratives, companies are no longer hidden powers that appear behind the scenes, but are reflected as entities with their own will and goals, and even those who try to achieve these goals through unethical means. “Quitters, Inc.” is presented from a dystopian perspective as a frightening example of this kind of corporate power that seeks profit but also establishes absolute authority over the lives of individuals.

King symbolizes this company, to express his sharp criticisms of systems that intervene in the name of the good of the individual, even against his will. The solutions offered by the company completely ignore the autonomy of the individual, turning him into a passive object that cannot make decisions on his own behalf. This is closely related to the criticism of bureaucracy and the system that we often encounter in the author’s other works. King shows how dangerous institutions that are inhumane, strictly bound by rules and have insufficient moral perspectives, managed by an authoritarian power, can be. Dick Morrison’s being stuck between the wheels of the company symbolizes the helplessness of the modern individual against the huge corporate structures that grow in the name of developing modernity and his having to submit to the rules imposed by the system due to the pressure on him.

Quitters, Inc. bears strong similarities to the basic themes of dystopian literature, with themes such as the erosion of individual freedom and the reflections of the oppression of authority. Works such as George Orwell’s *1984* and Aldous Huxley’s *Brave New World*, which are among the most powerful works of dystopian literature, are some of the best narratives of the pressure that totalitarian states or control systems exert on individuals and how identities are manipulated. The corporation in *Quitters, Inc.*, like the dystopian institutions in these stories, stands out with a system that infiltrates every aspect of an individual’s life, ignoring their privacy and keeping them under constant fear and surveillance. Especially in social and institutional dystopias, the idea that the commercial profit-oriented motivations of private institutions can lead to total social control is embodied in the concrete presence of the corporation in the story. The extreme forms of manipulation in the story are similar to those of manipulation today.

Although there are more subtle but widespread forms of social manipulation today, the ways in which manipulation is implemented are almost the same. Modern tools such as advertising, political advertisements or billboards, and social media applications are areas where human consent is often not obtained and are shaped by subtle psychological methods as a form of manipulation. Just as “Quitters, Inc.” broke Dick Morrison’s will directly or indirectly, today’s social media algorithms and marketing strategies can direct individuals’ consumption habits, political preferences, and even social interactions without regard to universal morality. This situation has increased concerns about the hidden erosion of individual freedom with the rise of technology’s influence on surveillance and control algorithms. Michel Foucault’s analyses of the physical and psychological disciplinary effects of modern power and surveillance mechanisms on individuals provide a critical perspective for understanding the foundations and goals of this invisible control (Foucault, 1995). King’s story gives the reader the task of not only being a reader, but also being a reader who invites them to question the power dynamics in modern society and the fragility of individual autonomy. With this goal, King sees the story as a means of awakening to explain how manipulation can be done by whom and therefore the need for more liberal social criticism. The most basic thing that is intended to be told in the story is that it is necessary to have an idea of how fear and control can shape the behavior of individuals in a social system.

5. STEPHEN KING’S LITERARY TECHNIQUE AND NARRATIVE STRATEGIES

Stephen King’s reputation in horror literature is not only related to the monsters or scary scenarios he creates, but also to his literary technique that skilfully penetrates the reader’s psychology. In the story *Quitters, Inc.*, King effectively demonstrates the dangers of manipulation and the delicate balance of individual freedom by using a simple and direct style, character-focused narrative, and his ability to create an atmosphere that makes the reader a part of the story. In this section, the strategies King uses in literature and how these strategies reinforce the main themes of the story have been analyzed and presented.

King’s literary mastery in *Quitters, Inc.* comes from using simple, understandable, and immediately relatable language, making the reader a part of the story instead of using complicated sentence structures or fancy descriptions to make them question. This style is a distinctive feature of King’s writing style when we look at all of his stories. He shows with his works that he has made it his style to infiltrate the theme of fear into the reader’s daily life and ordinary concerns. The fact that the main character of the story, Dick Morrison, is a typical American middle-class individual who gives the impression of everyone else, allows King to establish an immediate connection with the reader and affects the flow of the story. King makes it easier for the readers to put themselves in the character’s shoes by including Morrison’s inner thoughts and ordinary habits such as smoking addiction and work or family stress. This seemingly sincere and plain style of narration further increases the effect of the terrible manipulation methods applied by the company. These events occur in the ordinary life of an ordinary man and show that they can happen to anyone.

This linguistic simplicity also feeds King’s process of writing suspenseful stories. By avoiding unnecessary and ornate descriptions, he directs the focus to the plot and the inner terror experienced by the character without distracting the reader. This can be associated with the “unity of effect” principle used by Edgar Allan Poe in horror literature. Each word, and even each letter, serves a single emotion that the author aims to create in the reader (Poe, 1846). In *Quitters, Inc.*, this effect is reinforced by ensuring that the reader feels the same fear and helplessness as the character in each of the threats to Dick’s family.

One of King’s most important contributions to horror literature is his combination of physical fear with psychological depth. Although the company and its methods are an external threat in *Quitters, Inc.*, the real theme of fear in the story is related to Dick Morrison’s internal transformation and psychological collapse in the face of these threats.

By detailing the fears, anxieties and love for his family of his ordinary character, King emphasizes how manipulation deeply affects not only behaviours but also a person's state of mind and identity. Stephen King impressively describes how Dick's vulnerability to cigarettes evolved into his fear of harm to himself and his family. This is a striking literary representation of how manipulation reprograms the motivations and priorities of the individual in his inner world and his helplessness in the face of fear. The character's inner monologues and helplessness help the reader understand that manipulation is not just an ordinary power, but can also create a mental prison that can enslave the mind. The psychological layers in Stephen King's works and the confrontation of ordinary characters with their internalized fears are a frequently emphasized feature in King's criticism of fear and manipulation. Dick Morrison's situation also supports this view, as the individual's vulnerability to cigarette addiction or other addictions becomes a tool used by the company to manipulate him.

King prefers to use the technique of gradually building tension and fear in *Quitters, Inc.* At first, the company's promises seem like an attractive solution to Dick, but with each passing day and each new revelation, the company's true goal and ruthlessness of its methods are revealed. This process of revelation on every page keeps the reader's curiosity and tension constantly at the peak. After the company's first shocking threat, Dick's promise that he will never smoke again and the subsequent implication that he also leaves with a happy ending show that irony and black humour are also used in King's story. This so called "happy ending" is actually a part of manipulation and an ethically disturbing word. The fact that the "happy ending" is only for the act of quitting smoking and that the process is not evaluated in terms of morality can also be seen as a behind-the-scenes manipulation.

The presence of such surprise elements and the abundance of unexpected endings are seen as a distinctive feature of King's stories. Such endings not only scare the reader, but are also valuable in terms of giving them the ability to question. They leave the reader alone with moral and psychological dilemmas and thoughts about what is right and what is not. In *Quitters, Inc.*, the reader, left under the guise of "all is fair on this path," questions the freedom and peace that Dick lost, or perhaps never gained, as the price of quitting smoking. This situation shows King's ability to create a sense of fear not only with shocking moments, but also with permanent or temporary psychological effects and inferences that make the individual think.

6. CONCLUSION

Stephen King's short story *Quitters, Inc.* offers a profound work of social criticism that transforms the struggle to quit smoking addiction into a chilling allegory of institutional oppression and manipulation. Throughout this article, we have analyzed the control mechanisms and types of manipulation implemented by the company in the story in light of Foucault's surveillance theories and Skinner's conditioning principles, and examined the dangers of the consequences of fear, which is the main theme of the story. We discussed the erosion of individual autonomy and free will, the paradoxical determination of free will, and the dangerous aspects of the utilitarian ethics that legitimizes any means to achieve the goal. We also analyzed how the story functions as a powerful allegory of implicit or explicit institutional powers and dystopian forms of manipulation in modern societies. Finally, we discussed King's clear and simple language, his success in creating psychological depth, and his literary techniques based on gradual tension building, and how he effectively conveys these complex themes to the reader.

Although *Quitters, Inc.* appears to be about a successful treatment story that resulted in Dick Morrison quitting smoking, the real horror of the story lies in the price behind this success. While Morrison is trying to get rid of an addiction, he falls under the domination of a more sinister system that monitors and controls every moment of his life and shapes it with fear. The constant threats to his family and the loss of privacy cause him to cease being just a smoker and become no different than an object controlled by the system and deprived of his freedom.

Thus, King strikingly reveals how the individual's physical health can be restored at the expense of their psychological health and freedom, which can lead to irreversible consequences.

The story also contains extremely current and frightening warnings for today's contemporary world. In our age where artificial intelligence and algorithmic surveillance technologies are increasingly developed, it is becoming more possible to indirectly manipulate individuals' desires and needs, to secretly direct behaviours in many areas from consumption habits to political preferences, and especially to recommend treatment methods in the field of addiction. The dark dystopia of *Quitters, Inc.* stands out as a literary prediction that systems offered in the name of so called "goodness" or "efficiency" can erode the privacy and freedom of the individual. With this story, King not only offers the reader a narrative to read, but also encourages them to question the power dynamics in modern society, the fragility of individual autonomy, and the ethical cost of every solution offered. As a result, King's short story serves as a powerful warning that salvation does not always mean true freedom, and that true horror can lurk even in the most seemingly ordinary institutions closest to us.

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